

Deliverable D1.3

Project communication plan

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Date	Mvm	Who	Description
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1. Executive Summary

The B1MGplus project communication plan provides guidance and resources to support the effective communication of the project. Its objective is to act as a reference point for all aspects of B1MGplus communications, providing guidelines to partners internally and harmonising communications to users externally.

Through the document we present and discuss:

- Stakeholders, key messages and communications goals
- Communications channels
- Branding
- Communications assets
- Publications
- Public communications
- Evaluation

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the outcome, otherwise select 'No'.]

Outcome 1		Contributed
Supporting the Genome EDIC WG and the 1+MG Member States on the establishment of the EDIC by carrying out the field work required to generate high quality landscape and scoping documents necessary for the compliance framework beyond the legal creation of an EDIC. These documents will drive EDIC to become operational and offer compliant access to health and genomic data, covering legal, policy, quality and security aspects of data provision.	1. A record of processing activities that captures the legitimacy of EDIC and the corresponding safeguards	Yes
	2. A number of documents that can be fed back to the GDI Pillar I and/or the EDIC for discussion and/or adoption to provide legal tools and policies to govern the operations for suitable and specific safeguards to ensure the protection of the rights and freedoms of the data subjects whose data are included in the EDIC for secondary use.	Yes
	3. A framework that can guide the implementation of national IT infrastructure to ensure the quality and the security of workflows, tools and platforms.	Yes
Outcome 2		Contributed
WP2 will analyse the EHDS Regulation and will seek close exchange with relevant projects and stakeholders to investigate the conditions for a participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure, to give recommendations on the alignment of its policies, tools, security measures and IT framework with the requirements of the EHDS.	1. An analysis of the model how the EDIC could join the EHDS, its relationship with the various stakeholders and the conditions and opportunities of such participation	Yes
	2. Information on the practical consequences of the participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure	Yes

	3. Engaging public health professionals, and policy makers, in the discussion of benefits and challenges of adopting genomics in healthcare systems for clinical practice and public health policies	Yes
	4. Documenting the implementation of genomic medicine practices in national healthcare systems	Yes
	5. Promoting the awareness, literacy level and education of citizens on genomic medicine across Europe.	Yes
Outcome 3		Contributed
<p>WP3 will provide a framework of reference for genomics in healthcare that supports the decision making process, facilitating the definition of mid and long term targets and the path for genomics implementation, incorporating the feedback received from B1MG and the 1+MG experts.</p>	1. Mapping of gaps, challenges, unmet needs and solutions from the perspective of public health and healthcare professionals, healthcare systems and national genomic healthcare implementation programmes	Yes
	2. Recommendations for the EDIC on the uptake and implementation of genomics for healthcare and public health	Yes
	3. A citizen's hub for dissemination of genomic medicine, promoting citizens and patients awareness, literacy and trust	Yes
Outcome 4		Contributed
<p>The project will map existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to whole genome sequencing and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare. Building on the collected best practices, and together with experts in the field, the project will develop decision trees to be tested in national settings to guide decision making related to genomics in healthcare. The long term impact of the work is the scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare to support future prioritisation in healthcare, policy makers and decisions on investment in genomic medicine.</p>	1. Overview of literature and existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to WGS and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare	Yes
	2. Decision trees tested in national settings	Yes
	3. Scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare	Yes
Outcome 5		Contributed

Enhancing the 1+MG MLM for the implementation of genomics medicine in healthcare systems with updated domains and indicators, promoting its use and benchmarking by more healthcare systems. This will provide an homogeneous assessment framework that will foster the alignment of optimisation aims in healthcare systems across Europe, closing gaps, reducing asymmetries and ensuring a path towards equity of access to personalised medicine for all Europeans.	1. Updated 1+MG MLM incorporating novel dimensions aligned with emerging developments in genomic medicine	Yes
	2. Benchmarking of the MLM by healthcare systems across Europe	Yes
Outcome 6		Contributed
Expand the 1+MG Framework to fully define the 1+MG minimal metadata model, data standards, ontologies and quality criteria providing accessibility and maintenance, ensuring continuous alignment and support of 1+MG data use for research, innovation and policy making.	1. Phenotype data model	Yes
	2. Genotype data model	Yes
	3. Terms of use/ELSI metadata	Yes
	4. Software quality indicators for components to be incorporated into the 1+MG journey.	Yes
	5. Data/metadata provenance models	Yes

3. Methods

The Beyond One Million Genomes Plus (B1MGplus) project supports the creation of a European cross-border network of genomic and clinical data to improve healthcare outcomes. The project provides coordination and support to the 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG) Initiative¹, the commitment of 25 EU countries and Norway to enable secure access to genomic and corresponding clinical data across Europe.

To define the communications strategy, we build on:

- The experience and skills of the ELIXIR External Relations team
- The lesson learned from the delivery of the ELIXIR Hub portfolio of projects
- The specific project needs, defined by the different Work Packages, the coordination team, project partners and other projects and initiatives, such as the GDI project and 1+MG Initiative.

¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Stakeholders, key messages and communication goals

4.1.1 Stakeholders

The main B1MGplus stakeholders and target audience of communications are:

- Relevant European projects and initiatives, such as the 1+MG Initiative and its Working Groups, the GDI project, Genome of Europe, the European Health Data Space and TEHDAS2
- National genomic and personalised medicine programmes
- International initiatives, such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)
- Technical, scientific and clinical experts, including health data holders and data users
- Public and private stakeholders related to the creation of the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC)
- Public administrations (national, regional and local level)
- Genomic medicine educator
- Citizens, including patients

4.1.2 Key messages

The B1MGplus project's key objective is to support the 1+MG Initiative to advance data-driven healthcare solutions to benefit citizens of Europe. To achieve this goal, the project supports the 1+MG signatory countries to:

- Create a federated European genomics infrastructure based on an EDIC
- Develop guidelines for metadata, data and software standards and quality assurance
- Facilitate the uptake of genomics in healthcare delivery and public health policy
- Provide policy and legal frameworks to ensure secure, ethical data sharing

Key project activities include:

- Establishing a legal and policy framework to ensure genomic data sharing is secure and operational
- Building long-term sustainability by creating risk management strategies and strong stakeholder collaboration
- Advancing genomics in healthcare:
 - Raising awareness among healthcare professionals
 - Assessing and increasing the maturity of genomics adoption in healthcare systems
 - Creating a Citizen Hub to improve public understanding of and engagement in genomics
 - Demonstrating the economic benefits of genomic medicine in healthcare

- Developing data standards, such as robust ontologies, metadata guidelines and sequencing practices, for the 1+MG infrastructure

4.1.3 Communications goals

The main purpose of the B1MGplus communication activities is to build trust and awareness with project stakeholders and show how the project contributes to tackling societal challenges. The communication activities cover the communication and dissemination of the project's outcomes and impact to key stakeholders and beyond. The following impact categories are relevant to the B1MGplus project and can be applied to ensure the impact of the project's communications activities:

- Benefit of working together (also known as relationship capital): facilitate knowledge sharing and cooperation
- Bioinformatics resource uptake: work to increase their usage and appreciation by users
- Equal opportunity: raise awareness of diversity and inclusiveness
- Policy influence: ensure that policymakers are aware of the benefits of open science
- Public awareness: raise the public's awareness of genomics research, including their socio-economic benefits
- Research dissemination: ensure increased awareness of developments related to research infrastructure and its resources.
- Research efficiency: make infrastructure, resources and processes faster, easier to use and more integrated
- Research infrastructure sustainability: work to increase its visibility and appreciation by funders
- Skills development (also known as human capital): foster better skills for users and service providers

Stakeholders	Key messages and activities	Possible channels
Relevant European projects and initiatives/international initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop guidelines for metadata, data and software standards and quality assurance 	Website, social media, newsletter, meetings and conferences
National genomic and personalised medicine programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Facilitate the uptake of genomics in healthcare delivery and public health policy 	Website, newsletter and 1+MG Working group meetings
Technical, scientific and clinical experts (including health data holders and data users)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop guidelines for metadata, data and software standards and quality assurance ● Advance genomics in healthcare 	Website, social media, newsletter and conferences

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop data standards, such as robust ontologies, metadata guidelines and sequencing practices, for the 1+MG infrastructure 	
Public and private stakeholders related to the creation of the EDIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a federated European genomics infrastructure based on an EDIC 	Website, newsletter, 1+MG Working group meetings
Public administrations (national, regional and local level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a legal and policy framework to ensure genomic data sharing is secure and operational • Create a Citizen Hub to improve public understanding of and engagement in genomics 	Website, newsletter and social media
Genomic medicine educator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advance genomics in healthcare: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Raise awareness among healthcare professionals ○ Assess the maturity of genomics adoption in healthcare systems 	Website, newsletter, social media and conferences
Citizens, including patients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a Citizen Hub to improve public understanding of genomics • Demonstrate the economic benefits of genomic medicine in healthcare 	Website, newsletter and social media

4.2 Communications channels

4.2.1 Website

The primary communications channel for the B1MGplus project is the main website². The website provides comprehensive information about the project and will be the host for project news, updates and events. The primary goals of the website are:

- To communicate the B1MGplus project, its objectives and its organisation clearly.

² <http://b1mgplus.onemilliongenomes.eu>

- To promote activities and achievements of the project, for example, events and news stories of the project's progress.
- To advertise the impact of the B1MGplus project to key stakeholders, policymakers, funders and experts in health data and EDIC.

4.2.1.1 Website content

The ELIXIR Hub External Relations team is part of the B1MGplus Coordination Office (WP1) and has full editorial control over the website content. In developing new content, the ELIXIR Hub will regularly consult project partners and other relevant groups within the project. All materials to be published on the website should be sent to the ELIXIR Communications Officer (Zippy Tseng yun-yun.tseng@elixir-europe.org) and B1MGplus coordination (b1mgplus-coordination@elixir-europe.org).

4.2.1.2 Spelling conventions

The following conventions could be applied to the B1MGplus website as well as to other communication outputs.

- B1MGplus: B, M and G capitalised with plus in lower case and 1 in Arabic numeral.
- Use the English EC style guide³

4.2.2 Newsletter

The B1MGplus newsletter for internal and external stakeholders will be sent out quarterly. The newsletter will present news and updates of the project as well as activities and achievements. All content published in the newsletter must be directly related to the B1MGplus project, such as project news, latest deliverables, 1+MG Initiative news or updates from EU projects with which B1MGplus works closely. Announcements from other third parties will be considered if relevant to the mission or activities of the project.

The newsletter sign-up form⁴ is embedded in the website footer. The published issues will be available to view on the website. The newsletter is managed and created via the email marketing platform, MailerLite, and will be promoted via the B1MGplus website and social media channels.

The ELIXIR Hub is responsible for creating and managing the newsletter and the mailing list. The content for the newsletter is developed in consultation with Work Package leaders. In this context, ELIXIR Hub offers:

- A registration form for the mailing list for all partners, external stakeholders and interested parties to subscribe to the newsletter.
- Communications coverage to gather new subscribers, for example, promotion posts on social media.
- Provide a newsletter archive via the website.

³ https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2023-11/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf

⁴ <https://www.subscribepage.com/b1mgplus>

- A planning document and editorial calendar to programme a quarterly newsletter or special issues for key outputs of the project.

4.2.2.1 Target audience

The newsletter is open to subscription from any individual. The project is focused on a broad demographic of scientists (e.g. biologists, data scientists and social scientists) as well as policymakers and funders. Therefore, the newsletter content will be clear and accessible and contain links to further information on the B1MGplus website or the Zenodo community.

4.2.2.2 Newsletter template

A template for the B1MGplus newsletter has been created and will be used for the project newsletters. Contents listed in the template include, but are not limited to:

- Project highlights: to present the key outputs of the project or the upcoming events.
- Project news: to share updates from Work Packages and project partners as well as collaborations with other EU projects.
- Recommended events: to promote events organised by other organisations that are of interest to the B1MGplus project stakeholders.
- Recommended reads: to disseminate the B1MGplus project publications or other publications related to the 1+MG Initiative or EHDS.

4.2.3 Social media

The B1MGplus project's social media strategy focuses on promoting the project's activities, driving more visitors to the website as well as community building and networking. Since the B1MGplus project is a continuation of the Beyond One Million Genome (B1MG) project, the audience on social media is likely to be similar. In order to maintain the followers accumulated during the B1MG project, the B1MGplus project reused B1MG's X and LinkedIn accounts with new account handles.

- X: @B1MGplus⁵
- LinkedIn: B1MGplus Project⁶

Since the change in ownership of X (formerly Twitter) in October 2022, there has been a move away from the platform. The B1MGplus project will focus its social media strategy on LinkedIn and with some cross-posting on X. Currently, there is no Bluesky account (one of the most used X alternatives) due to the time necessary to build an audience. However, key project outputs will be shared on Bluesky via the ELIXIR account to reach the potential audience on the platform.

4.2.3.1 Hashtags

The project has close relations with the 1+MG Initiative and the hashtag [#1MGenomes](#) should be used in posts related to the initiative. The hashtag will bring up existing posts from

⁵ <https://x.com/B1MGplus>

⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/b1mgplus-project>

the B1MG project, the GDI project and the European Commission referring to the 1+MG Working Group.

As a project funded under the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme, [#DigitalEU](#) will be used in posts when mentioning outputs of the project.

Other hashtags are keywords related to B1MGplus and its key objectives, for example [#genomics](#), [#genomicdata](#), [#healthdata](#) or [#EHDS](#). Hashtags related to the project’s outcomes or events can be created in the future when needed.

4.2.3.2 Tagging

Whenever possible and relevant, social media posts should tag partners and/or project groups whose work is being communicated, such as the following accounts:

Organisation	X	LinkedIn
ELIXIR	@ELIXIREurope	@ELIXIR Europe
European Commission	@EU_Commission	@European Commission
EMBL-EBI	@emlebi	@European Bioinformatics Institute EMBL-EBI
SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB)		@SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
Barcelona Supercomputing Center	@BSC_CNS	@Barcelona Supercomputing Center
Health-RI		@Health-RI
Sciensano	@sciensano	@Sciensano
Institut National de la Sante et de la Recherche Medicale (INSERM)	@Inserm	@INSERM
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)	@CNRsocial_ @elixir_it	@Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche @/company/elixir-iib/
BioData.pt	@BioDataPT	@BioData.pt

A full list of project partners' X handles⁷ has been created and can be found on the B1MGplus X account.

4.3 Branding

4.3.1 Logo

The B1MGplus project logo mirrors the updated branding of the 1+MG Initiative by adopting the same colour scheme and reflecting the key concept of the project with the DNA helix in the logo.

1+MG Initiative logos

B1MGplus project logos

The B1MGplus logo and 1+MG Initiative logo are available on the project Google Drive⁸.

4.3.2 Brand guide

The B1MGplus brand guide⁹ follows the updated 1+MG Initiative brand guide. It is available on the project Google Drive for project partners to easily lift logos, design and funding acknowledgement for their presentations.

⁷ <https://x.com/i/lists/1331964496022278144>

⁸ https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1wwk2RD4BZIPchdmiCaGGc3jO_djSHZZA

⁹ https://drive.google.com/file/d/14ytpaqk8EjXk7duSB-9lN5iuan3yQqHx/view?usp=drive_link

Project partners are also welcome to reach out to the Communications Officer at the ELIXIR Hub should they require further visual materials or assistance in developing presentations for the B1MGplus project.

4.3.3 Templates

The ELIXIR Hub provides templates for a range of communication activities and reports that follow the brand guide. All B1MGplus presentations should use the official template. The templates are available on the project Google Drive⁸, including:

- Presentation slides
- Documents
- Deliverables
- Milestones

4.4 Communications assets

4.4.1 Graphics, icons and stock images

As detailed in Section 4.3, the B1MGplus logo and branding guidelines are available on the project's Google Drive to facilitate the correct usage of the B1MGplus branding.

Requests for further materials and details on their usage can be directed to the ELIXIR Communications Officer (yun-yun.tseng@elixir-europe.org) or the B1MGplus Project Manager (b1mgplus-coordination@elixir-europe.org).

4.4.2 Boilerplate text

The B1MGplus boilerplate text can be reused in new contexts or applications without any significant changes. Examples of use include project partners' websites, news and press releases and publications.

Boilerplate text:

The Beyond 1 Million Genomes plus (B1MGplus) project is helping create a European cross-border network of genomic and corresponding clinical data to improve healthcare outcomes. The project provides coordination and support to the 1+ Million Genomes Initiative, which is the commitment of 25 EU countries plus Norway to enable secure access to genomic and corresponding clinical data across Europe, supporting research, health policy and personalised healthcare.

4.5 Publications

Publications can help increase awareness and publicity of technical knowledge resulting from project implementation. Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to and funded by the B1MGplus project

must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement.

B1MGplus acknowledgement for communications activities:

“ B1MGplus project receives funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101194865.”

4.5.1 Zenodo

Zenodo will be used as a home for project outputs, such as deliverables, posters, presentation slides, training materials and other related documents. Efforts will be made to ensure outputs are published in a timely manner, ensuring good visibility and impact, for example, sharing links to Zenodo documents of the B1MGplus website and social media.

4.6 Public communication

One of the main activities of the B1MGplus project is to facilitate the uptake of genomics for healthcare. The project will achieve this by promoting awareness and engagement of public health professionals through communication activities on the project website and social media as well as attending conferences.

Additionally a Citizen Hub will be created by WP3 to stimulate public engagement and debate on clinical genomics and increase public awareness regarding its societal impact. The Citizen Hub will also bring together materials that have been developed in various national and international projects, such as GDI, GoE, EOSC4Cancer, PROPHET and others. Further information on public engagement of the project will be detailed in the WP3 deliverable. The project’s communications team in WP1 will help disseminate and promote the Citizen Hub through the project website, social media, newsletters and other existing networks.

4.7 Evaluation

The evaluation of B1MGplus communications will be carried out continuously. It will summarise and analyse the impact of each communication channel and provide information for the D1.4 Project communications strategy review.

4.7.1 Communication metrics

The communication metrics will measure the engagement rate, the quality of communications and the reach outside the B1MGplus project. Data collected will include:

- Website traffic metrics
- Performance of the B1MGplus newsletter provided by MailerLite
 - Subscribers
 - Click rate
 - Open rate
 - Benchmark with other comparable newsletters

- Social media analysis (LinkedIn and X)
 - Followers
 - Number of posts
 - Post impressions and engagement rate
- Zenodo analysis
 - Views
 - Download

4.7.2 Communication and dissemination progress

To monitor B1MGplus project partners' communication and dissemination efforts, a B1MGplus reporting tracker¹⁰ will be monitored by the B1MGplus project management team.

5. Conclusion

The communication plan defines the communications channels, the B1MGplus branding, the communications assets, the evaluation criteria and the communication guidance that together provide the means for effective internal and external communication. The evaluation criteria will be used to monitor the effectiveness of the communication strategy and provide the means to act and ensure that the communication strategy remains fit for the purpose throughout the project.

At the moment of writing, this communication strategy (June 2025 - M05 of the B1MGplus project), the strategy is already in place and being used across all WPs, such as WP meetings and the BMGplus kick-off meeting. In the coming months, we will evaluate the effectiveness of the communication channels and use this information to improve the strategy.

6. Next steps

The ELIXIR Communications Officer will continue to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the project communication strategy. The evaluation of the communications strategy and recommendations will be included in D1.4 Project communications plan review.

¹⁰

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1-3NyAyGqSSdGXktOplvjTut6S-tjf7tADY53MJRLtZA/edit?gid=1819726455#gid=1819726455>

